

T1 mapping with radial Open-MOLLI

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Reproducibility of T1 mapping is crucial for the clinical validity of the quantification. However, it is dependent on the standardization of MR sequences which have been shown to introduce high measurement variability.¹ Vendor-neutral sequences can be an alternative since it has been shown to improve inter-vendor and multi-center reproducibility.^{2,3} In the context of myocardial T1 mapping, the recently developed Open-MOLLI⁴ has shown to provide similar and reproducible values to the standard MOLLI sequence, and it opens up the opportunity of this measurement strategy in different MRI scanners and centres. However, the inversion recovery framework of MOLLI presents a few drawbacks such as biased maps due to the typical fitting strategies and sensitivity to motion. One way to improve the flexibility and robustness of this sequence is the use of a radial sampling trajectory. This has the potential to decrease the acquisition time and improve accuracy through the application of more complex reconstruction algorithms based on the extended phase graphs framework.⁵ In this work, we extend the Open-MOLLI implementation to allow a radial sampling trajectory and tested it in vivo in 6 healthy subjects.

METHODS: Open-MOLLI uses inversion and triggering schemes based on the MOLLI sequence, developed in Pulseseq⁶ (<https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>). Open-MOLLI was modified to perform a radial trajectory with golden angle (i.e. 111.25°) sampling. Acquisitions were performed in a Siemens Aera 1.5 T. Both phantom (ISMRM/NIST Phantom) and in vivo acquisitions (calf and the heart) were performed. Parameters: TR/TE=3.04/1.52 ms, bSSFP readout with flip angle of 35° , slice thickness of 8 mm, 354×327 mm² field-of-view, 256×144 matrix size; 200 spokes. Clinical MOLLI was obtained with TR/TE=3.2/1.6 ms. Offline reconstruction with NUFFT and parameter mapping estimation were performed. Time of inversion was considered as matching the spoke in the centre of the acquisition window.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: Figure 1a shows T1 maps obtained with the radial trajectory for the phantom where the values are similar to the ones presented for Cartesian Open-MOLLI and MOLLI, with mean T1 values for vial 3 ($T1^{\text{ref}}=1027$ ms) of $T1^{\text{MOLLI}}=1100 \pm 17$ ms vs $T1^{\text{Cartesian Open-MOLLI}}=990 \pm 18$ ms vs $T1^{\text{radial Open-MOLLI}}=1258 \pm 21$ ms. The overestimation observed when compared with MOLLI and Cartesian Open-MOLLI may be related with the variation in T1-weighting introduced since all the spokes sample the centre of k-space. T1 maps of the calf (Fig1b) show T1 values of the muscle similar between the three sequences tested. Further work will be performed to evaluate the need for additional gradient and phase corrections.

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Figure 1 – T1 maps (ms) obtained for **a.** ISMRM/NIST phantom and **b.** calf, with MOLLI, Cartesian Open-MOLLI and radial Open-MOLLI. The arrows indicate vial#3 with reference value ($T1^{\text{ref}}=1027$ ms) similar to the T1 of healthy myocardium.

References

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